

Data Management Plan for 2024/2025 postdoctoral studies of a liquid metal free surface electromagnetic stabilization

Version 0

Description

This data management plan describes how data is collected and stored in the first postdoctoral project of Dr. Arturs Brekis. The project is 1 year long and realized in the framework of Internal and External Consolidation grants of the University of Latvia.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0002
Electromagn. stabiliz. studies
of a liquid metal free surface
for applications in
thermoacoustically driven
magnetohydrodynamic
generator

Researchers

Arturs Brekis (orcid:0000-0002-3098-3242)

Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management Plan for 2024/2025 postdoctoral studies of a liquid metal free surface electromagnetic stabilization

Description:

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Contact: Arturs Brekis

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0002 Electromagn. stabiliz. studies of a liquid metal free surface for applications in thermoacoustically driven magnetohydrodynamic generator

Project:

3. License

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Publication Date: 2024-11-05

4. Templates

Descriptions

Description of collected data for Work Package Nr.1 - Solid body electrodynamic tests with electrically conducting rod

A traveling wave thermoacoustic (TAc) engine using argon gas coupled with a 200W, low-power, magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) generator using liquid sodium (Na) forms a novel electricity generation technology called "SpaceTRIPS." This technology has no moving parts. It works due to the Na oscillations in a magnetic field, thus generating electrical power. This working principle was first time in the world demonstrated at the Institute of Physics, University of Latvia, during an ambitious international EU project: "Space Thermoacoustic Radio Isotopic Power System," aimed for electrical power supply for deep Space missions. During "SpaceTRIPS", several disadvantages have been identified. The main problem of the TAc+MHD generator is the existence of a liquid metal free surface and the free surface instability that develops during the pressure oscillations generated by the TAc engine. This postdoctoral project aims to research these drawbacks and propose a solution using electromagnetic stabilization. A surface stabilization method will be developed to improve the generator's operation. This can raise the TAc+MHD technology readiness level to at least 3-4 in the future. A series of numerical MHD simulations are planned, and an experimental session will be conducted, performing liquid metal free surface stabilization tests in a 5T superconducting DC magnet. The main findings will be submitted for publishing, and the results will be presented in at least one international conference.

Here will be given description of how data will collected during the Work Package (WP) 1 preliminary experiments and mathematical modelling, and how they will be stored. In this experimental campaign there will be made test with electrically conductive rod and its interaction with permanent magnet magnetic field. At first there will be made test of free fall, while measuring time when magnet is falling on the rod. During this fall there will be electromagnetic interaction, that will result in induced electric currents inside the electric conductor. This current will interact with magnetic field and create a dragging force, that will slow down the fall. The next test will be done with oscillating motion of the rod inside of the magnetic field created by permanent magnets. In this case there will be displacement measured in millimeters as a function of frequency.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: Dataset

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The postdoctoral project proposal aims to study the possibilities of the electromagnetic stabilization of the liquid metal free surface. The aim is to offer a practical solution for eliminating the critical shortcomings of the thermoacoustic-MHD energy converter, thus increasing its competitiveness and increasing the TRL level. Various configuration and operating principle methods of stabilizing the surface of an oscillating electrically conductive liquid using an external magnetic field will be investigated. The hypothesis of the project proposal is the following: With an applied magnetic field, it is possible to stabilize the free surface of the oscillating electrically conductive liquid. To demonstrate and research this principle, numerical and experimental studies will be carried out with strong MHD interaction on the free surface of the liquid. This will be done using a specially designed experimental modeling stand with a specifically built fluid motion drive mechanism. The experiment will be performed using an external magnetic field provided by the IPUL superconducting magnet.

However, before tests in strong magnetic field, there will be performed test with electrically conductive, solid rod and its interaction with magnetic field created by permanent magnet. This will be done in this work package. The purpose is to better understand the electromagnetic interaction of this type of phenomena that it relevant to "SpaceTRIPS" technology, that is the base of this research.

There will be performed measurements such as breaking force, as well as photo and video recordings of the experiments. Also there will be performed timing experiments with time measurements of the electromagnetic transient processes, such as measurement of time during the cylindrical rod dropping time, while dropping through the ring-shaped permanent magnet.

During the 1st Work Package there are 3 tasks in this postdoctoral project. This dataset will be devoted to data collected during these tasks.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Other

Photographies and videofiles during experiment

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- txt
- pdf
- xls
- jpg

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

I don't have plans to re-use any existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To other academic researchers who are working on similar problems, as well as industry representatives, who are interested in collaboration and development of similar technologies.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

There will be created txt. files, that will be added to the experimental and modelling data. They will include precise description with details what exactly was done. For example - how strong magnetic field was. Or what oscillation frequency was used.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

The Zenodo is chosen due to it's availability, free of cost and easy-to-use interface and convenience. It is checked, that it is registered in <https://www.re3data.org/> as well as <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/> platforms, that ensures high data set security and compliance with project requirements.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

It will be needed to access txt. files with measurement data. Also photographs and video files will be available, that will be able to open with simple and common media players.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The txt. files that will be generated will be available to open them with any software similar to Excell, Notepad or similar.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

It is decided to be chosen the same as for whole data management plan. It is assumed that it is allowed to be freely used, but with reference to the author.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-09-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The responsibility of making data FAIR will be on the project leader. The postdoctoral researcher will be managing data collection and checking them for

the correspondence to the FAIR principles during his paid daily working time, during the whole project implementation, whenever it will be necessary.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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The postdoctoral researcher will collect, postprocess (if necessary) and deposit all data collected during the research process. This will include, for example, taking video reels and photo shoots during the electrodynamic experiments in the work package. After taking the photos, the quality of the photos will be checked and if necessary a new set of experiments will be made and new data will be collected.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The data repository "Zenodo" is chosen to be free of cost for permanent data storage.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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